

The Effect of Diversity Sensitive Orientation on Job Satisfaction and Turnover Intention

Hyeondal Jeong, Yoonjung Baek

Abstract—The main purpose of this paper is to examine the effect of diversity sensitive orientation on job satisfaction and turnover intention. Diversity sensitive orientation is the attitude of the individual to respect and accommodate diversity. This is focused on an individual's perception of diversity. Although being made from the most diversity related research team and organizational level, this study deals with diversity issues at the individual level. To test the proposed research model and hypothesis, the data were collected from 291 Korean employees. The study conducted a confirmatory factor analysis for the validity test. Furthermore, structural equation modeling (SEM) was employed to test the hypothesized relationship in the conceptual model. The results of this paper were as followings: First, diversity sensitive orientation was positively related to job satisfaction. Second, diversity sensitive orientation was negatively related to turnover intention. In other words, the positive influence of the diversity sensitive orientation has been verified. Based on the findings, this study suggested implications and directions for future research.

Keywords—Diversity sensitive orientation, job satisfaction, turnover intention, perception, cognition.

I. INTRODUCTION

FIRMS to achieve competitive advantage by hiring their various members. As the increase in diversity in the organization, studies on diversity has also consistently being made. Diversity-related studies have been mainly studied in a team or organizational level [1], [2]. In previous studies by calculating the heterogeneity of team or organization through diversity objective measures (Blau Index and Entropy Index) and utilize it for analysis [3]. However, group members will be different because the reactions and perceptions of each individual objective similarity [4], the diversity research is needed at the individual level. Therefore, the present study is to prove whether understanding and accommodating the diversity of its members have any impact on job attitudes. As an initial study of the diversity sensitive orientation (DSO), examine the relationship between diversity sensitive orientation and job attitude (job satisfaction & turnover intention). If the positive influence the verification of diversity sensitive orientation, in future studies will need to examine the relationships with more variables.

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II. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND AND HYPOTHESIS

A. Diversity Sensitive Orientation

Sung defined diversity sensitive orientation as “Psychological attitude within the organization members to respect and acceptance for diversity” [5]. Research on diversity sensitive orientation being made in some empirical studies, but is lacking. According to previous studies, diversity sensitive orientation is having a positive effect on individual creativity [6]; it was also affects the human resource management variables such as diversity initiatives [7].

B. Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction means to achieve a pleasant emotional states are getting value for their job [8]. Job satisfaction is there to predict the behavior and attitudes of members through a number of previous studies has been considered an important factor [9]. In addition, job satisfaction has a positive impact on organizational performance. According to previous studies, antecedents of job satisfaction vary (leadership, organizational characteristics, working conditions, etc.).

C. Turnover Intention

Turnover is shown as an external action. However, turnover intention is the psychological state of individuals who are not into action. In other words, employees are defined as intended to leave in the current workplace [10]. According to past research, perceived organizational support (POS) has a negative effect on turnover intention [11]. The results are visible inferred that protective factors are organizational support to reduce the turnover intention.

D. Diversity Sensitive Orientation and Job Attitudes

Diversity can be explained mainly through the Social Identity Theory (SIT), by showing people similar to themselves who for the in-group favoritism [12]. According to the previous studies it was mainly analyzed that diversity on a negative impact on the performance or the attitude variables [13], [14]. Research from diversity sensitive orientation is a subjective perception by recognition of the importance of the individual members [15]. Cognitive and perception is important because it influences the attitudes and behavior of its members. In the field of organizational behavior theories that are related to perception attribution theory of leadership, charismatic leadership, procedural justice theory, and the like. Diversity within the organization generates conflicts among members [1], [16]. If you accepted diversity, it will have a positive impact on the dependent variable? That is, if you accept and respect the

other members, job satisfaction is increased, and also the turnover intention will decrease (Fig. 1).

- Hypothesis 1. Diversity sensitive orientation will exhibit a positive, statistically significant relationship to Job satisfaction.
- Hypothesis 2. Diversity sensitive orientation will exhibit a negative, statistically significant relationship to Turnover intention.

Fig. 1 Research model

III. METHOD

A. Sample and Data Collection

The samples are collected through questionnaires of Korean employees. Voluntary survey research was conducted with approximately 400 workers. A total of 291 individuals completed surveys, yielding a participation rate of 72.7%. Most participation were 31 to 40 years old (38%) and had 5 to 10 years of work experience (30%). Additionally, 62% of participants were university graduates.

B. Measures

All variables are measured in a 5-point Likert scale.

- **Diversity sensitive orientation.** Diversity sensitive orientation was measured with ten items developed by [5]. The scale's reliability in the present sample was excellent (Cronbach's alpha =.91, e.g. "It tries to respect and accommodate differences in the race").
- **Job satisfaction.** Job satisfaction was measured with ten items developed by [17]. The scale's reliability in the present sample was excellent (Cronbach's alpha =.81, e.g., "Generally speaking, I'm satisfied with my current job").
- **Turnover intention.** Turnover intention was measured with four items developed by [18]. The scale's reliability in the present sample was excellent (Cronbach's alpha =.85, e.g., "I often think about quitting this organization").

IV. RESULTS

This study used AMOS 21.0 & SPSS 18.0 with maximum likelihood estimation to analyze the research model (structural equation modeling). According to confirmatory factor analysis (CFA), several scale items were removed due to low factor loadings. In addition average variance extracted (AVE) was calculated to test the convergent validity of the results. All AVE scores were above .537, suggesting good convergent validity of the results. The study's results all exhibited adequate fit measures (NFI of .91, IFI of .94, TLI of .92, CFI of .94, and RMSEA of .077), as shown in Table I. All variable were correlated with each other between -.292 and .162 at the level of $p < .01$, Cronbach's alpha was used to check the internal consistency of measurement items. All measures revealed adequate internal reliability ($\alpha \geq .70$), as seen in the diagonals of Table II.

TABLE I
CONFIRMATORY FACTOR ANALYSIS (N=291)

Confirmatory Factor Analysis (n=291) Variable	Item	Non-standardized factor loading	S.E.	C.R.	P	Standardized Factor loading	AVE	Construct reliability
Diversity sensitive orientation	dso2	1.271	0.104	12.228	***	0.874	.624	.908
	dso3	1.254	0.103	12.225	***	0.878		
	dso4	1.069	0.096	11.145	***	0.781		
	dso8	1.089	0.097	11.250	***	0.782		
	dso9	1.125	0.1	11.196	***	0.777		
	dso10	1	-	-	-	0.646		
Job satisfaction	js2	0.76	0.079	9.580	***	0.650	.537	.851
	js4	0.802	0.091	8.787	***	0.589		
	js7	0.75	0.078	9.677	***	0.658		
	js8	1.154	0.100	11.490	***	0.848		
	js9	1	-	-	-	0.680		
Turnover intention	ti1	1	-	-	-	0.861	.599	.817
	ti2	0.902	0.061	14.856	***	0.832		
	ti4	0.799	0.058	13.737	***	0.757		
Model fit	$\chi^2=200.894(df=72, p<0.001)$, CMIN/DF=2.790, NFI=.912, IFI=.942, TLI=.926, CFI=.941, RMSEA=.079							

*** $p < .001$

The structural equation modeling was used in this study are shown in Fig. 2.

Hypotheses testing results of this study showed positive, significant relationship between diversity sensitive orientation

and job satisfaction ($\beta = .204, p < .01$). Also, negative, significant relationship between diversity sensitive orientation and turnover intention ($\beta = -.267, p < .001$), as shown in Table III. All

hypotheses were supported; the positive influence of the diversity sensitive orientation was confirmed.

Model fit was utilized in hypothesis testing $\chi^2 = 189.723$ (df = 70, $p < .001$), CMIN/DF = 2.710, NFI = .917, IFI = .946, CFI = .945, RMSEA = .077. All index showed a good level of fitness (CMIN/DF is 3 below, NFI, IFI, CFI is .90 over, RMSEA is .050 ~.080, if we can accept the model) [19].

TABLE II
 MEANS, STANDARD DEVIATIONS, AND CORRELATIONS

Variables	Mean	S.D.	1	2	3
1. Diversity sensitive orientation	3.433	.839	1(.913)		
2. Job satisfaction	3.489	.675	.162**	1(.814)	
3. Turnover intention	3.200	1.034	-.200**	-.292***	1(.857)

n=291, *** $p < .001$, ** $p < .01$, () : Cronbach's alpha

Fig. 2 Structural equation modeling

TABLE III
 RESULTS OF STRUCTURAL EQUATION MODELING ANALYSIS

Path	Non-standardized factor loading	S.E.	C.R.	Standardized factor loading
H1. DSO → Job satisfaction	.160	.054	2.958**	.204
H2. DSO → Turnover intention	-.425	.107	-3.960***	-.267
Model fit	$\chi^2=189.723$ (df=70, $p < 0.001$), CMIN/DF=2.710, NFI=.917, IFI=.946, TLI=.929, CFI=.945, RMSEA=.077			

n=291, *** $p < .001$, ** $p < .01$

V. DISCUSSION

A. Implications

Looking at the implications of this study are as follows. First, theoretical implications of this study are meaningful research diversity at the individual level. Diversity-related research, most of the research team or organizational level they constitute the majority. However, this research has concerned how a person receives diversity. Analysis results of the current research were the higher degree of diversity reception verified positively influence the outcome variable. In order to explain the influence of the diversity described by social categorization theory [20] and similarity attraction theory [21], but the diversity in individual levels can be explained through cognitive theory. By validating the positive impact of Diversity Sensitive Orientation it has expanded the diversity of research. Second, looking at the practical implications, the positive influence of the diversity sensitive orientation (DSO) was confirmed. Organization managers should try creating an

atmosphere that can accommodate the diversity or reduce the heterogeneity due to diversity through diversity-related training programs.

B. Limitations and Directions for Future Research

This study follows a limitation to generalize the results because the samples collected in the target area of some employees of South Korea. In addition, with all the variables measured in the same time, there is a problem in the Common Method Bias. These limits will have to be supplemented in future research.

Exploring future research based on analysis results, and are as follows. Because confirm the positive influence of the diversity sensitive orientation (DSO) in future research studies it should be expanded to reveal the relationship between the various outcome variables. For example, studies reveal the antecedent variable of diversity sensitive orientation (DSO), effect the relationship between diversity sensitive orientation (DSO) and outcome variables will be extended to study for identifying contingency variables. Through this research, we expect DSO-related research is actively proceeding.

VI. CONCLUSION

The positive impact of diversity sensitive orientation analysis was verified. These results will have a positive impact on diversity sensitive orientation (DSO) the behaviors and attitudes of employees. In other words what is important is that the individual is aware of the diversity. Therefore, diversity of research at individual level should be done actively. Studies on the diversity sensitive orientation are initial step. Therefore, in future research it is necessary to use various dependent variables expand their research.

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